

ROCK PAINTINGS OF THE IRON AND BRONZE AGE

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Anotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ilk temir davri tarixi, uni kelib chiqish xususiyatlari va temir davri arxeologiyasi va bronza davridagi qoyatosh suratlari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar yoritilgan.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье освещается история раннего железного века, особенности его происхождения, а также сведения об археологии железного века и наскальных рисунках эпохи бронзы.*

Abstract: *This article covers the history of the early Iron Age, the features of its origin, and information about the archeology of the Iron Age and the rock paintings of the Bronze Age.*

Kalit so'zlar; *Temir metalli, ikkinchi mehnat taqsimoti, ayirboshlash va savdo aloqalari, ko'chmanchi chorvachilik, Urartu podsholigi, temir davri yodgorliklari.*

Ключевые слова; *Железный металл, второе разделение труда, обмен и торговые отношения, кочевое скотоводство, царство Урарту, памятники железного века.*

Key words; *Iron metal, the second division of labor, exchange and trade relations, nomadic animal husbandry, the kingdom of Urartu, monuments of the Iron Age.*

During the Iron Age, great technological changes took place in production. Compared to copper and tin, iron ore is abundant in nature, and its solid quality has led to its rapid and wide spread in the production and military spheres. The transition to the use of heavy weapons, especially in agriculture, was a big event. Because during the expansion of farming areas, iron tools and weapons (axe, hoe, spade), especially strong tools such as plow with iron teeth appeared. In the Iron Age, handicrafts were separated from agriculture and separate production. turned into a farm. The development of industrial enterprises with the wide distribution of iron undoubtedly led to a radical change in social life. Large villages became centers of trade and trade, and cities grew. They were surrounded by high and thick walls made of clay and straw [1]. Thus, the large-scale use of iron and steel products had an effective effect on the development of the cities and villages of Central Asia. S.P. Tolstov, A.I. Terenozhkin and Ya. It was carried out by the Ghulomovs. Monuments of the Iron Age in the territory of Uzbekistan. av. It belongs to the 8th and 6th centuries. They were studied in Khorezm, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent regions and Fergana Valley; Like Kozaliqir, Qal'aliqir and Dingilja. castle and village, city ruins, Tagisken and Uygarak cemeteries, Bokantov rock paintings were examined. In the Iron Age The first large irrigation facilities were built in Khorezm regions. Ancient people were familiar with metal as early as the Neolithic period. But the discovery of metallurgy and the acquisition of complex metallurgical skills took place in later periods. Iron is a unique metal. Its properties determine its advantage over other metals. Iron metal is abundant in nature. Of course, it was widely distributed not in the finished form, but in the form of ore. It is extracted from iron ore in a dark state and crushed in sandons. As we know, bronze objects were poured into molds in a liquid state. The melting temperature of iron is 1534°C, and the combat and labor weapons made of it have superior properties compared to the previously existing weapons due to their

hardness and sharpness. The discovery of iron as a new type of metal not only changed the material culture of its time, but also created new opportunities for technology. It laid the groundwork for socio-economic changes that took place in the following millennia. Iron was harder and sharper than its predecessors, and it was widely distributed on the earth. But people adopted it after other metals. According to written sources and archaeological data, iron metallurgy was established in the territory of the Hittite kingdom in Asia Minor. avv. It was created in the XIV-XIII centuries. Mil. avv. Iron metal was discovered in India and Iran in X-IX centuries. Mil. avv. In the IX-VIII centuries, blacksmithing was widespread in Assyria and Urartu. Mil. avv. All iron products made in the 14th century are extremely valuable art jewelry. The widespread use of iron weapons in social life, as work tools and weapons, was implemented relatively late. For example, iron in Italy in the 12th century BC, in Eastern Europe, Scandinavian countries. avv. It appeared in the 10th century.

And in China, mil. avv. Iron products were produced in VI-V centuries. It is known from sources that iron weapons began to be used here in the 9th century BC. In the Early Iron Age, agriculture and handicrafts became the main areas of production, which led to the development of society to a new level. Handicrafts took the main place in economic life and created wide opportunities for exchange. First, he developed the productive forces of productive economy and handicrafts. Handicraft products - pottery and smithy became products produced for exchange and began to acquire the character of a commodity. Because, during this period, the production possibilities reached such a level that the income from one person's work was not enough to feed him alone, but to provide for several people. Due to the beginning of the emergence of separate craft centers and their transformation into the economic basis of city life, an opportunity was created to establish trade relations. The production of many products served the development of trade relations. The state of Urartu was one of the largest kingdoms of the early Iron Age. The word Urartu is Assyrian, Urartian - Biaynili, in the Bible - the kingdom of Ararat. An ancient state in Western Asia (IX-VI centuries BC). During its prosperity, the state of Urartu covered the mountainous regions of Armenia (the entire territory of present-day Armenia, part of Turkey and Iran). The inhabitants were mainly Urartians. Its capital was the city of Tushpa (now the city of Van in Turkey), where large construction works were carried out during the reign of King Sarduri I. Mil. avv. At the end of the 9th century - the first half of the 8th century, the state of Urartu flourished. During the reigns of Menuya, Argishti I and Sarduri II, the territory of Urartu expanded considerably. Fortresses were built in the occupied regions (the city of Menuakhinili on the northern slope of Mount Ararat; Erebuni - Arin-berd hill near Yerevan; Argishtikhinili on the left bank of Araks). Slave labor was widely used in Urartu. Mil. avv. In the middle of the 8th century, the Assyrian king Tiglathpalasar III (745-727 BC) defeated the Urartu armies several times and occupied Northern Mesopotamia and Northern Syria, which were part of the Urartu state [2]. Then, during the reign of Rusa I, the country was destroyed as a result of the marches of the Assyrian troops of Sargon II. But mil. avv. In the 7th century, Urartu still maintained its position in South Transcaucasia. Rusa II (685-645 BC) built new fortresses here (including Teyshebaini). With the help of the Scythian-Cimmerian mercenary army, the kings of Urartu crushed the Kingdom of Phrygia (676 BC). The rise of the Median kingdom brought Urartu closer to Assyria. But mil. avv. At the beginning of the 6th century, Urartu was crushed by the Medes and annexed to it.

In Central Asia, the first working tools made of iron were found in monuments belonging to the IX-VIII centuries BC. But most of the objects belong to the VII-VI centuries BC. The first Iron Age in Central Asia is defined as the 1st millennium BC. Dozens of monuments such as Anov, Dalvarzin, Daratepa, Quysisoy were studied in the southern regions of the Republic of Turkmenistan, Kashkadarya and Zarafshan oasis of Uzbekistan, Fergana Valley and

Tashkent and Khorezm regions. 46 of the monuments from the beginning of the 1st millennium BC were found in the regions of Southern Turkmenistan. The cultural layers in ancient village ruins such as Anov, Yoztepa, Yelkantepa, Uchtepa, Chornoq belong to the Iron Age. One of the monuments of the Iron Age is Yoztepa, the lower layer of which is dated to 900-650 BC. During this period, the monument consisted of village dwellings occupying an area of 16 hectares and a large rectangular building-fort. Remains of a palace built on an 8 m high raw brick platform were found on the site of the fortress. The rooms were long and square [3]. Most of the ceramics of the Summer I period were made by hand. The vessels are painted with yellow angob and a geometrical pattern is applied over the angob with brown and red paint. Many monuments of the early Iron Age have been found in the territory of Uzbekistan. Afrosiyab, Daratepa, Kozalikir, Uygarak, Chust, Dalvarzin, Oktom, Kuchuktepa, Yerqorgan, Sangirtepa monuments belong to this period. At the end of the 2nd millennium BC and the beginning of the 1st millennium BC, the Chust culture in the Fergana valley was the first farming culture in Ancient Fergana, and the first village of the peasants was named Buvanamozor near the city of Chust in 1951 by the archaeologist M. Ye. Voronev. It is found and studied by the spring. There are more than 70 monuments belonging to this culture in Namangan, Andijan, and Fergana regions, about 10 of which were researched by archaeologists V. Sprishevskiy, B. Matboboev, and Yu. Zadneprovskiy. According to archaeologists, BC. Military-political tribal associations were formed among the nomads in the 7th-6th centuries. The study of Tagisken tombs is of great importance in studying the history of nomadic tribes [4]. The mausoleum dates back to the millennium BC. It belongs to the IX-VII centuries and was found in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya. They are rectangular mausoleums made of raw bricks. The material culture of the early Iron Age tribes living in Central Asia was found and investigated in the lands of Bactria, Margiya and Sogdiya.

There are more than 350 of them. Horse equipment, arrows, and daggers found in the places of the Sak tribes are similar to the Scythian weapons that lived in the steppes of Eastern Europe and Asia. The Greek historian Herodotus c. Avv. It provides information about the life of the Scythians in the 5th century. Important written sources - Avesta, written monuments of the Achaemenid period and Greek historians tell about the society in the ancient regions of the early Iron Age of Central Asia. "Avesta" (translated as "Esos" from Eastern Iranian languages) is a set of Sharia laws of the peoples of Zoroastrian religion. According to the Avesta, the union of tribes of this period was a region (dahiya), a clan community was made up of a vis, and some families were made up of a nmana. The population was divided into priests, warriors, farmers and herders. The cuneiform inscriptions of the Achaemenid period (VI-IV centuries BC) were found and examined in Behistun and Nakhshi Rostam rocks, in the cities of Susa, Hamadan, and Persepolis. They consist of the king's orders and speeches on various social, political, and religious issues in ancient Persian [5]. There is information about the peoples and regions of Central Asia from the writings of the Ahmanids. The works of ancient Greek historians Herodotus and Ctesius show the historical and geographical features of the peoples of Central Asia. The study of the material and cultural monuments of the Early Iron Age indicates that during this period great social, economic and cultural changes took place in the life of the peoples of Central Asia [6].

During this period, the agricultural culture based on artificial irrigation led to the increase of additional products and private property. The cultures of Sopollitepa, Jarqo'ton, Kuzamshir, Afrosiyob, Dalvarzin and Chust indicate that many metal weapons and objects were produced in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan. Work tools made of metal led to an increase in labor productivity and a change in people's lifestyle. During the 3rd-2nd millennia BC, one of the main branches of handicrafts, pottery, developed and the pottery wheel became widespread. Trade, which played an important role in the strengthening of urban culture and

statehood, became the main means of economic, social, political and cultural communication not only with the region, but also with other regions and countries [7]. Of course, in the formation of the foundations of statehood and the rise of urban culture, not only the changes in production relations (agriculture and crafts) and the development of trade, but also the natural-geographical location of our region and the western-strategic (conflict of Eastern and Western interests)) also played an important role. The oldest cities in these socio-political, economic and cultural changes and the emergence of the first statehood were: Sopollitepa, Jarqo'ton (Surkhandarya), Yerkurgan, Uzunqir (Kashkadarya), Kukhatepa, Afrosiyob (Samarkand) and other cities. hna cities played an important role.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Annayev T., Shaydullayev Sh. Surxondaryo tarixidan lavhalar. – T.,1997.
2. Asqarov A. Eng qadimgi shahar. – T., 1990.
3. Jo'raqulov M., Isomiddinov M. O'rta Osiyo kulolchiligi tarixidan. – Samarqand, 4. Isomiddinov M.H. Sopolga bitilgan tarix. – T., 1993.
5. Kabirov J., Sagdullayev A. O'rta Osiyo arxeologiyasi. – T., 1990.
6. Eshov B.J. Qadimgi O'rta Osiyoning shaharlari tarixi. – T., 2006.
7. Qadimgi tarixchilar O'rta Osiyo haqida. – T., 2008.